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Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'zbek tilshunosligi va badiiy adabiyotining o'zaro munosabati yoritib berilgan. Unda tilshunoslikdagi badiiy til uslubiy belgilari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: muloqot, so'zlashuv jarayoni, emotsionallik, ekspressivlik, lingvopoetika, fonopoetika, fonostilistika, fonopoetika.

Аннотация: В статье описывается взаимосвязь узбекского языкознания и художественной литературы. В ней рассматриваются стилистические особенности художественного языка в языкознании.

Ключевые слова: общение, речевой процесс, эмоциональность, экспрессивность, лингвопоэтика, фонопоэтика, фоностилистика, фонопоэтика.

Annotation: The article describes the relationship between Uzbek linguistics and fiction. It examines the stylistic features of artistic language in linguistics.

Key words: communication, speech process, emotionality, expressiveness, linguopoetics, phonopoetics, phonostylistics, phonopoetics.

Emotional-expressiveness in normal daily conversation features are not needed. Because in everyday life, it has become common for people to base their speech on a number of principles such as brevity, accuracy, simplicity and fluency. If we use positively colored words more than the norm in our daily life, the style of our speech can be broken. But the creator can use all aspects of the language, speech formulas characteristic of all styles in fiction¹. A skilled writer uses emotional and expressive factors and connotative meanings of words in the speech process to affect the reader emotionally through the language of the literary work.

It is known that general issues of linguopoetics have been studied a lot in world linguistics. In particular, in a number of works devoted to lexical poetics, text poetics, phonetic stylistics, and phonosemantics, linguists have a lot of studies focused on the science of sound symbolism, alliteration, gemination, and rhyme. In most works in the field of linguopoetics, especially in phonopoetics, it is emphasized that the mental and acoustic-articulatory aspects of each language are fundamentally different from each other. It is natural that hundreds of languages in the world have their own characteristics in their own differential signs.

The importance of integration in the development of sciences is being adequately demonstrated. As a result of the study of linguistics in relation with several fields, sociolinguistics, linguoculturalology, neurolinguistics, psycholinguistics, as well as linguopoetics, which is a general philological direction, and phonopoetics in particular, were deeply researched. In this dissertation, the limits of phonopoetics and phonostylistics were shown, and the fact that phonopoetics, as a sub-field and component of linguopoetics, is an important task of philology, is expressed through examples.

¹ Nurmonov A. Selected works. II - vol. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2012. p. 231.

In recent years, along with studying the internal structural units of the Uzbek language from a communicative point of view, understanding their emotional-expressive functions, connotative and pragmatic meanings is of great importance in illuminating the colorful side of the language. The emotional-expressive tasks of linguistic units are realized in different styles in artistic works and this requires a linguopoetic analysis. Phonopoetics, which is considered a branch of the field, is close to the fact that the poetic possibilities of phonetic units have not yet been sufficiently explored in Uzbek phonopoetics². The phonopoetic analysis of artistic texts, which are a part of our national culture and spirituality, is important for today's Uzbek linguistics.

A lot of work is being done for the perfect study of artistic speech in the field of linguopoetics of Uzbek linguistics. Scientific-theoretical opinions that covering all the linguistic possibilities of the artistic language is its most important feature have come to the fore.³

The stories of the famous writer Abdulla Qahhor occupy a special place in literary studies due to their sharp and impressive language and the fact that they cover real life events. The writer has a story called "Speech". We pay attention to the following excerpt from this story. In the speech of the hero of the play, the elements of formal style are skillfully used: "What achievements have you and I achieved as a result of our one-year family activity?" First of all, it should be noted that we have come to solve fundamental disagreements on this or that issue directly, without attracting external forces, with our own strength, through extensive mutual observation. My wife, we have strengthened our family to an unprecedented level in terms of organizational economy..."

In Cholpon's poem "Gozal", the emotional state of the lyrical hero is revealed through the repeated use of the lexeme of love in one verse:

*Men yo'qsil na bo'lib uni suyibmen,
Uningchun yonibmen, yonib-kuyibmen,
Boshimni zo'r ishga berib qo'yibmen,
Men suyib ...men suyib, kimni suyibmen?
Men suygan suyukli shunchalar go'zal,
Oydan-da go'zaldir, kundanda go'zal!*

At the lexical level, the effective use of lexemes, exaggeration, simile, and other artistic elements increases the impact of the artistic language and the attractiveness of the image. For example, in Abdulla Oripov's poem "My first love", he created analogies by comparing the world to a castle without holes, or in the poem "Bahar" the stars, which are the lights of the sky, to a crystal button on a uvada vest. At the heart of these linguopoetic situations lies the goal of avoiding simplicity, liveliness, and enriching the artistic speech with rich and colorful poetic elements, to attract the reader's attention.

So, mankind has been given a priceless gift called consciousness and awareness. A person may or may not express all the thoughts in the mental thought process. As there are so many heavenly bodies in the universe: planets, comets, asteroids, stars, etc., the emergence of the day and the development of the green world depend only on the solar system. The selection of words related to the speech process and the transmission of information also depend on the speaker. As a means of communication, language has not only simple symbols, but it is also a powerful tool to

² Tursunova O.A. Poetic possibilities of phonetic units of the Uzbek language. Philol. science. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) thesis. Fergana, 2019. p. 12.

³ Nurmonov A. Selected works. II - vol. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2012. p. 234.

influence the listener. It is at this point that we can notice the connection between linguistics and literature.

The emotional-expressive function of artistic speech is expressed more by phonetic means, tone. Phonetic means are the main relevant (important, significant) signs of artistic discourse, elements that create speech beauty. Therefore, not only the lexical poetics part of linguopoetics, which studies the emotional-aesthetic function of a certain language, which has attracted the attention of more specialists, but also the parts of phonopoetics, morphopoetics and syntactic poetics should become the object of serious research.

Among the special phonopoetic tools that provide emotional expressiveness, such tools as euphony, accent, tone, stop have a strong psychological effect on the listener⁴.

"Language is the king on the chessboard for style," says Fedin⁵.

How to form the artistic language, how to influence the reader's psychology and worldview through words can be said to be the criterion that determines the professional skills of writers and poets.

References

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⁴ Tursunova O.A. Poetic possibilities of phonetic units of the Uzbek language. Philol. science. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) thesis. Fergana, 2019. p. 12.

⁵ Jamolkhanov H. Modern Uzbek literary language. Book 1. - Tashkent, 2008.